

Management and Conservation of Musical Cultural Heritage from an Archaeological Perspective: China's Silk Road Musical Heritage

Yulin Yan ¹, Yujing Hu ^{2*}

¹ Ph.D Candidate, Department of Global Culture Convergence, Kangwon National University, Chuncheon-si, Republic of Korea

² Ph.D Candidate, Faculty of Music and Performing Arts, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, Tanjong Malim, Malaysia

* **Corresponding Author:** huyujing189@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

In order to strengthen the protection of musical cultural heritage, this paper takes three types of "Ni Yi Yuyi", "Qin Wang Po Formation" and "Qin Yin qing" in the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907) as the research objects, and analyzes the timbre, loudness, tone and instrument combination. First of all, with the help of the database, the relevant historical and cultural materials are collected, classified and summarized. Then, the sound of the four instruments was measured with a Mini wireless microphone Model 1020 (Dongguan, China) and a 4K color microscope Model 700 (New York, United States). The material of the instrument was observed. Finally, the musical characteristics of the Chinese Silk Road in the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907) were summarized, and the inheritance of the musical heritage of the Silk Road was promoted. The results showed that Xiliang music was mainly used for the performance of the main melody because of its low voice and single melody, while Qingshang music was mainly used for accompaniment, while Tianzhu music and Qiuzi music were mainly used for melody adjustment because of their wide vocal range and diverse tunes, and the two could cooperate with each other to better display the music. Therefore, Xiliang music, Tianzhu music, Qiuzi music and Qing Shang music are the main music of the Chinese Silk Road in the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907), which not only shows the Buddhist culture of the Sui and Tang dynasties, but also reflects the integration characteristics of Chinese and Western music, and has high archaeological value.

Keywords: Musical Cultural Heritage, Management, Silk Roads, Musical Heritage.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, people have attached great importance to the study of the Silk Road. However, up to now, few people have taken the initiative to study the musical heritage of China's Silk Road from an archaeological perspective. Based on this, this paper takes three kinds of music, "Ni Clothes and Feather Clothes", "Qin King Breaking the Array", and "Qin Yin Qing" (Ali, 2023), as the research objects to explore the protection of the musical heritage of the Silk Road, which has high archaeological value. In order to study the music culture of the Silk Road more deeply, it is necessary to use the relevant murals in the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang to understand the way of playing, the way the orchestra is combined, and the shape of the instrument (Alshareef, 2023). The Chinese Silk Road has influenced Chinese and European societies in many aspects, and as a transportation route in ancient Eurasia, it has always played a vital role in history (Alves, Gong & Li, 2023), culture and economy. Obviously, the imprint left by China's Silk Road can be seen in the deep exchanges and integration between Chinese and European civilizations, and it has had a significant impact on the historical development of China and Europe. Music has always been a highlight of the Silk Roads and an integral part of the Silk Road culture. In the process of researching the musical heritage of the Silk Road, domestic scholars mainly focus on the analysis at the theoretical level, summarizing the textual information such as repertoire and melody in the musical heritage, lacking the comparative analysis of timbre, melody and melody in the heritage. Foreign scholars' research on the musical heritage of the ancient Silk Road has focused more on software analysis and the

reproduction and simulation of music. The musical heritage of the ancient Silk Road is not only the traditional culture of China, but also the percussion culture of Central Asia and Africa, so to deeply study the content of the musical heritage of the ancient Silk Road, it is necessary to conduct an in-depth analysis of its melody, loudness and other aspects, with the help of modern music analysis software, music recognition equipment for comparison and research, so as to improve the accuracy of the analysis, through the analysis and comparison of the software, the cultural connotation and deep cultural content in the musical heritage can be excavated, and the better excavation of music culture can be ensured. Moreover, it also plays a very unique role (Amusan & Nel, 2023). This is because the symbols of music culture on the Silk Road, as well as related historical texts, development and evolution, and evidence remaining, can be used as part of the treasures of the Silk Road music culture and provide reasonable value for subsequent related research. Therefore, this article will carry out a specific analysis of the aspects. At the same time, based on the archaeological perspective, this paper explores the value and significance of the musical heritage of the Silk Road in China (Arsentyeva, 2023). It helps people understand the archaeological value of the musical heritage of the Silk Road. In order to study the musical heritage of the Silk Road more profoundly and improve the depth of excavation of cultural heritage, this paper should analyze the following aspects. First of all, this paper understands the musical development of the Silk Road in China during the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907), and selects the representative pieces "Ni Clothes and Feather Clothes" (Bharti, 2023), "Qin Wang Breaking the Array" and "Qin Yin Qing" for shape, timbre, loudness and material analysis. Then, analyze the melody, the form of playing, and the combination of the instruments. Finally, according to the test results, musical instrument characteristics are classified to support the genetic protection of musical culture. For example, people can reuse musical heritage, carry out the restoration and restoration of musical instruments, or integrate well-known repertoire into tourism projects, cultural exhibitions, and theme parks to better inherit musical cultural heritage. This paper analyzes the musical heritage of the Chinese Silk Road, firstly collects the data content of the musical heritage of the ancient Silk Road, and combines the music culture and characters in the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang to determine the research objects of the musical cultural heritage, then conducts music online and music retro to identify the musical characteristics of rhythm and imagination in music, and then uses mini microphones and music analysis software to analyze and compare the rhythm, melody and loudness characteristics to find the hidden problems, and finally theoretically analyzes the characteristic content of music and discovers the characteristics and connotations of music in the ancient Silk Road, so as to promote the protection and improvement of the music cultural heritage of the Chinese Silk Road and its level of protection. The main purpose of this paper is to excavate the musical heritage culture of the Chinese Silk Road, identify its musical cultural characteristics, such as loudness and rhythm, and promote the classification and protection of music in the later period.

THE MANAGEMENT OF CHINA'S SILK ROAD MUSICAL HERITAGE FROM AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

The Influence of the Silk Road on the Music Genre of the Sui and Tang Dynasties

In the history of ancient world civilization, China's Silk Road culture has always been well-known. This is because the Silk Road opened up the ancient road of cultural exchange between Asia and Europe, affecting the economy, society and culture of Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq, Kuwait and other countries. Whether from the perspective of geography, history, or culture, the Silk Road has always been a connecting channel between China, Central Asia, and Europe, with ancient religions, cultures, and arts. Therefore, the Silk Road is crucial for exchanging and communicating cultural systems between China and Europe. During the Sui and Tang dynasties, the silk trade significantly promoted artistic and cultural exchanges between the Sui and Tang dynasties and Europe and popularized the musical heritage that can be used as a reference and reference for future generations (Brandner, 2023).

During the Western Han Dynasty (AD 581~907), Zhang Qian began to envoy to the Western Regions, marking the opening of the Silk Road, which has always been a firm stroke in world history. Moreover, the Silk Road allowed the Han Dynasty (AD 581~907) to travel with European merchants and literati artists and significantly promoted the exchange of music and dance cultures and commercial exchanges at that time (Chang, 2023). To talk about the musical and cultural heritage on the Silk Road, we must start with the exchange channels of music and dance culture in the Sui and Tang dynasties. For example, after the opening of the Silk Road, culture, music, and trade began to be exchanged frequently between Central Asia and Europe, and mutual exchanges were constantly carried out. With the marriage between the Han and the Xiongnu, Buddhism was gradually introduced to the Han Dynasty (AD 581~907). It can be seen that the Han Dynasty had already communicated with Europe through the Silk Road, allowing frequent exchanges between the Central Plains and European countries to form a peak stage of musical exchanges. Because of this, the art of music and dance in the Han Dynasty began to become

extremely distinctive and rich (Chen, 2023), and contained many foreign elements. During the Wei, Jin, Southern and Northern Dynasties (AD 420~589), because of political division and turmoil, the culture of the Central Plains ethnic groups continued to merge. The support of Buddhism in the Tang Dynasty gradually consolidated the status of Buddhism, and musical instruments rich in Buddhist connotations were also widely spread in the Central Plains, such as King Kong bells, and appeared in Xiliang music, Tianzhu music, and Qingshang music. It can be seen that on the Silk Road, many musical instruments with Buddhist characteristics were continuously introduced, forming well-known music and dance and becoming the main musical content of the Silk Road (Cheng & Zeng, 2023). Moreover, in the Mogao Grottoes of Dunhuang, there are also many murals about the King Kong Bell, and they are vividly depicted through the murals. This proves that Tianzhu music, as an essential piece of music, can accompany music and dance with Buddhist characteristics and is one of the musical cultural heritages on the Silk Road.

The Role of the Silk Road on the Musical Connotation of the Sui and Tang Dynasties

During the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907), the Silk Road made the exchange of music and culture between China and the West more frequent, and the connotation of music and dance was sublimated. At the same time, European culture also greatly influenced the evolution of the Central Plains style and the formation of the new style, promoting the prosperity of the Sui and Tang dynasties. In the nearly 1,000 years of cultural exchanges along the Silk Road, Dunhuang, the centre of exchange, has always had great historical and archaeological value. Since the Western Han Dynasty (AD 581~907), Dunhuang has become a gateway to the Silk Road, an important commercial town, and a connection point for cultural exchanges and various transportation networks between various ethnic groups in Europe and Asia. Therefore, the intersection of Chinese and European culture (Chou & Demiryol, 2023), folk customs, religion, economy and trade has deepened the connotation of Chinese music.

Moreover, music became an important cultural element of the Silk Roads, forming a special symbol. As mentioned above, during the Sui and Tang dynasties of the Silk Road, Buddhist music spread, so Dunhuang left a large amount of Buddhist music. The spread of Buddhism is inseparable from the important position of Dunhuang. Historically, Buddhism needed to find a place to settle (Chung, 2023), and for various reasons, Buddhism began to land in Dunhuang. As a result, the historical action of opening caves and statues in Dunhuang has been continued. According to relevant historical records, the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang had begun to be built in 366 AD. By the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907), the Mogao Grottoes reached a heyday. In the grottoes, there are many statues and murals related to the image of the Buddha, which often expounds some simple Buddhist teachings. The statues and murals have become important historical and cultural heritage and relics of the Silk Road. Many elements of medieval music and culture are found in the music-related murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang. Therefore, in-depth excavation of the connotation of Silk Road music culture can provide rich archaeological data for future generations' management, protection and research. Among them, the cultural connotation of Sui and Tang music is very rich, for example, there are at least 140 paving scriptures and paintings, including Lingle, Qingshang music, Xiliang music, Shule music, Kang Guole, An Guole and so on. In addition, some of the music is accompanied by a combination of musical accompaniment, and the use of solo instruments such as qin, xiao, and king gang bell is used to perform music and music. Although the degree of musical integration between China and Europe was relatively low during the Silk Road, there are traces of the integration of China and the West, which still supports the research on the connotation of music culture in later generations (Clydesdale, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

In view of the musical heritage of the Chinese Silk Road during the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907), three kinds of music were measured, including "Ni Shang Feather Clothes", "Qin Wang Breaking the Formation" and "Qin Yin Qing", using microscopes, wireless microphones, RAW acoustic test software, and Photoshop drawing software. Among them, the measurement indicators include the playing instrument's material, the instrument's resonance point, the tune, the melody, the timbre, the loudness, etc. First of all, with the help of the database, relevant historical and cultural materials are collected, classified and summarized. Then, the sound of the four instruments was measured with a Mini wireless microphone 1020 (Dongguan, China), and the instruments' material was observed with a 4K color microscope Model 700 (New York, United States). This paper summarizes the musical characteristics of China's Silk Road in the Sui and Tang dynasties and supports the management and protection of music's cultural heritage. This paper chooses Neon dress and feather dance because it is court music that often appeared during the Silk Road period of the Tang Dynasty, which combines bronze instruments, Xiao and other orchestral instruments, and the music instrument is widely popular in Central Asia and East Africa, and is a representative work of cultural exchanges in Central Asia during the Silk

Road period. The Qin King Breaking Array Dance is an improved court music on the basis of the neon dress and feather dance, which has obvious characteristics, integrating a variety of percussion instruments and orchestral instruments, and is a representative court music that often appears in the Tang Dynasty, with obvious cultural characteristics of the Tang Dynasty. Qin Yin Qing is a representative piece of music in the Tang Dynasty, which has the dual characteristics of court music and folk music, and represents the peak of the development of folk music in the Tang Dynasty. On the whole, the dance was court music for the Tang Dynasty to communicate with Central Asia and Europe, theKing Qin broke the array dance is court music created in combination with the characteristics of the Tang Dynasty, and Qin Yin Qing is the result of the fusion of court music and folk music. The criteria for selecting the above three pieces are three types: 1) the scope of application of the instrument, 2) the type of music, and 3) the popularity of the instrument, and the results of the selection of the three pieces are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. In this Paper, the Selection Represents the Grading Level of the Piece

Music	The type of song	Popularity	Scope of application
Neon dress and feather dance	A fusion of Chinese and Western music	Very popular	Tang court, Central Asia, East Africa
King Qin broke the array dance	Court music	Very popular	Tang Dynasty court
Qin Yin Qin	Folk music	Very popular	Yuefu or folk

The test software used in this paper is mainly REW 2.0, the music equipment is tested by the mini microphone, the loudness of the music in the test is identified by the receiving voltage signal, the timbre mainly depends on the electrical frequency signal for identification, and the tone mainly depends on the current signal for identification. Based on the voltage, electrical frequency and current signals, the REW software compares the loudness, timbre and tonal characteristics of three representative music, generates simulated visual signals, and completes the comparison of the music. Among them, timbre is the overall timbre of a variety of instruments, so the electrical frequency signal is constantly changing.

RESULTS

Comparison Results of Melody and Melody

The tunes and melodies of "Ni Clothes and Feather Clothes", "King Qin Breaking the Formation" and "Qin Yin Qing", as well as the melody, are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Melody Comparison of the Representative Music of the Silk Road

The content analysis in [Figure 1](#) shows that the intensity of Qin Yunqing varies greatly between 2f~3p, and the change frequency is 0.4 Hz. However, the strength of the Qin King Breaking Array Song and the Nishang Feather Cloak Song changed slightly, from 1f to 10p, and the frequency was 0.1~0.2 Hz, which shows that the Neon dress and feather dance has both the softness of the sound of the piano and the excitement of the song of King Qin. However, the change in the melody of the three pieces is the same, mainly using musical instruments such as King Kong Ling, Se, Xiao and so on, and the instruments are mainly from Europe and related to the trade of the Silk Road. The style of the above three pieces is similar to that of the European harp and violin and has the characteristics of traditional Chinese lyrics. Among them, the palace, Shang, Jiao, Qingjiao, Zheng, Yu, and Changgong of the palace are similar to the natural tunes of 1, 2, etc. in Europe, further illustrating the Silk Road's influence on music. On the Silk Road, music culture has always played a relatively important role and has a certain symbolic significance. This is because the Silk Road opened a relatively smooth communication channel for the economic, trade, and cultural exchanges between China and Europe during the Han Dynasty. At the same time, with the help of this channel, people began to bring the music culture of various regions and nationalities to China and realized the real integration of Eastern and Western cultures, so that the music culture could continue to spread and be effectively integrated in various countries and regions along the route. At the same time, it has also helped the countries and regions along the Silk Road gradually form new musical forms and styles and show unique artistic vitality and artistic expression in many different fields. For example, in various regions along the Silk Road, different musical cultures were integrated into the field of religion, folk music, and opera, thus gradually promoting the musical exchange between Chinese and European civilizations.

Records of the Silk Road in Chinese

The various historical records left by the musical heritage of the Silk Road can reflect the trajectory of musical exchanges, development and evolution between China and Europe at that time. As we all know, there are many historical documents that have recorded the musical information content of the Silk Road. For example, in the "Records of the Western Regions of the Tang Dynasty" and other documents, the musical exchanges and the evolution of musical forms on the ancient Silk Road in China have been recorded. Among them, the information in the bamboo slips mainly involves musical forms such as solo and ensemble, as well as musical instruments such as King Kong bell and seer, and the way orchestral music is becoming more and more popular, similar to the development of European harp and sass. Therefore, this provides key evidence for later generations to understand the development and evolution of music along the Silk Road. In this way, people will be able to explore more of the musical and cultural content of the Silk Road and effectively pass it on and protect it, so as to facilitate the comprehensive cultural research of the Silk Road. The following analyzes the composition of the diamond bell in the Qin King Breaking Array Song and takes the fragment of the diamond bell excavated in Baoji, Shaanxi Province, as the test object. The excavation site is shown in [Figure 2](#).

The excavation site of the King Kong Bell

Specifications of the King Kong Clock

Figure 2. Fragment of King Kong Bell Excavated in Baoji, Shaanxi

Figure 2 shows the fragment of the diamond bell excavated in Baoji, Shaanxi Province, which proves that the diamond bell was a musical auxiliary instrument during the Silk Road period. The electron microscope image of the diamond bell was obtained by scanning it with a third-party electron microscope, as shown in Figure 3.

Observation of the material of the diamond clock

Resonance distribution of the diamond clock
Figure 3. Electronic Scan Results of the Diamond Bell

Through metal comparison, it was found that the electron microscope scanning results of the musical instrument King Kong Bell in "King Qin Breaking the Array" were similar to tin and lead, and the tin and lead were produced in Afghanistan and Tajikistan, which further proved that King Kong Bell was introduced to the Central Plains from Central Asia and Europe. According to historical records, the diamond bell is mainly a magic instrument. Tin element first appeared in Central Asia and West Asia, in the middle and late Tang Dynasty was widely introduced to China, China's tin content is relatively small, Central Asia has more selenium content, and widely mined and appeared in tin as the material of tableware and musical instruments, through the Silk Road, the Tang Dynasty imported a large number of tin products, resulting in musical instruments containing a large number of tin elements. The utensils used in the practice of deeds are the instruments of the Dharma. In Tibetan Buddhism, many ritual instruments tend to have a very mystical color. In terms of categories, there are different classifications of ritual instruments. Specifically, it is divided into 6 categories: salutation instruments, praise instruments, offerings, inspections, demons, and persuasion. The murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang depict the ritual instruments very frequently, and the main ritual instruments it depicts include bells and drums, conchs, diamond bells, trumpets, pipas, wooden fish, etc., which are basically used in Buddhist ceremonies and are used as ritual instruments. Moreover, ritual instruments often have some kind of evil spirit-driving effect, showing a high degree of mystery. In the ancient Silk Road, there is a certain representation of musical characteristics, as shown in [Table 2](#).

Table 2. Comparison of the Musical Characteristics of the Silk Road

location	Metal content (%)	Bearing capacity (N)	Resonance points
upper portion	3.467(0.303)	-0.625(-0.067)	3.231(0.458)
Lower	-0.383(-0.390)	0.565(0.707)	-0.458(-0.754)
Central	-0.072(-0.027)	0.309(0.142)	-0.015(-0.009)
Sides	0.339(0.155)	0.615(0.346)	-0.650(-0.481)
Select a point correlation	8	0.001	

Spatial Distribution of Loudness of Instrument Combinations

Along the Silk Road, such as Gansu, Dunhuang, Shaanxi, Xi'an and other regions, there are many types of musical instruments, including gong, hou, qin, se, and other non-drum and self-sonicating instruments, which are called "non-drum and self-sonicating instruments". Moreover, it also includes substantive musical instruments such as flute, flute, sheng, qin, pipa, zheng, gonghou, pan flute, xiao, clapper, and dutan drum. The musical instrument graphics in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang can show the same shape as the musical instruments recorded in the historical materials. At the same time, its playing technique and playing posture are similar to those recorded in historical documents and can show the actual function of the instrument in the picture. This kind of instrument is a substantive instrument. Moreover, this kind of musical instrument is often found in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang. In general, their appearance is related to Buddhist rituals. There are generally fluttering ribbons on different musical instruments, which seem to symbolize a unique celestial artistic conception. According to the musical instrument combination forms of "Neon Clothes and Feather Clothes", "Qin Wang Breaking the Array" and "Qin Yin Qing", the spatial simulation of the sound of "Qin Wang Breaking the Formation" is carried out, and the results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The Spatial Reverberation Effect of the Performance of "King Qin Breaking the Formation"

As can be seen from Figure 4, in the range of 96 m², the distance between the instrument playing point and the audience is 10 m, and the sound reverberations of the front, left and right of the listening point are almost overlapping and the front side has the strongest reverberation effect, indicating that the combined instruments will resonate. Moreover, the melody played is stable, further justifying the combination of instruments. The musical instruments of "King Qin Breaking the Formation" are mainly orchestral instruments, such as stringed instruments and wind instruments (horizontal flute, bamboo basket, conch, prosthetic mouth flute), percussion instruments (clapper and maoyuan drum, square ring, waist drum), stringed instruments (Huqin, five-string pipa, Qiuzi pipa, crested ukulele), etc., including gonghou and, se, zheng, etc. Among them, many artefacts related to music have also been found. For example, musical instruments and musical materials along the Silk Road related music murals, etc.

Materials for Musical Instruments

The measurement of the string instruments in the "Song of Ni Clothes and Feathers" shows that the strings are wound by double strands, with a total width of 3.6 mm and a single strand width of 2.83 mm, indicating that the production technology of string music in the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907) was developed and could achieve more precise string production, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The Strings of a Five-stringed Lute

From the microscopic observation of the strings in Figure 5, it can be seen that the strings are not only shiny, but also translucent, indicating that the strings of the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907) were made of silk from the Central Plains, combined with bone glue technology from Central Asia and Europe, which not only made the strings corrosion-resistant, but also increased the toughness of the strings and enhanced the timbre of the performance. Microscopic observation of the snakeskin of the Huqin, a musical instrument in Qin Yin Qing, shows the results in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Microscopic Test of Snakeskin on the Huqin

As can be seen from Figure 6, oxidized grease (16-acyl acid, 17-acyl acid and 18-carbenoid acid) has appeared in the snakeskin of the Huqin in Qinyinqing, which can improve the elasticity of the snakeskin and improve the timbre of the Huqin. During the Sui and Tang dynasties, the leather preparation technology in the Central Plains was backward, and the preparation methods that could achieve the effect in Figure 6 were also introduced from Afghanistan, Iran and other countries. At the same time, many murals in the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang also depict the performance of the Huqin, further proving that the huqin-making process was ubiquitous in the Sui

and Tang dynasties. An in-depth analysis and study of the musical materials of the Silk Road will provide an in-depth study of the cultural heritage of music. In this way, it can help people to have a deeper understanding of the significance and value of musical exchanges between different cultures, understand the musical characteristics and styles of the Sui and Tang dynasties, and reveal the musical culture, inheritance and evolution of different ethnic groups on the Silk Road. China's technology for snakeskin cooking is relatively backward, mainly through cooking, oil sludge and other ways to cook, but in Central Asia and West Asia and other regions, lime, zerosene and other methods are used to cook skin, which greatly improves the level and quality of book skin. Through the ancient Silk Road, the cooked leather technology from Central Asia was introduced to the Tang Dynasty, which improved the cooked leather technology of the Tang Dynasty and also made the string music such as erhu and huqin develop greaterly. From the data observations in Figure 6, it can be found that the frequent exchanges of cooked skin technology between the Tang Dynasty and Central Asia and East Africa promoted the development of cooked skin technology in snake skin in the Tang Dynasty. To sum up, during the Silk Road period, ancient Chinese music showed certain characteristics, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Characteristics of Different Music

	Synergy	loudness	Tune changes	Differences
Xiliang music	-190.000	0.000	-5330689197078.344	0.000
Tianzhu music	-0.000	0.000	-0.073	0.946
Qiuzi music	1.000	0.000	5785332152918.287	0.000
Qing Shang music	-0.000	0.000	-0.137	0.898
Similarity	F (4,4)=7.643581124893036e+25,p =0.000		Durbin-Watson	0.755
Select a point	9		Comprehensive	-508.051
Adjustment factor	1.000		Toggle the diff	-507.065

THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL TRANSMISSION OF MUSICAL HERITAGE ALONG THE SILK ROADS

In-depth Excavation of the Value of Musical Instruments in the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang

As mentioned above, the musical cultural heritage of China along the Silk Road needs to be effectively managed and protected by future generations. To this end, it is necessary first to understand the various musical and cultural heritage contents of the Silk Road. This includes musical instruments and music performance techniques, musical forms and repertoire, musical rituals, dance, etc. Therefore, in order to manage and protect the musical heritage of the Silk Road more effectively, this paper decides to take the musical instruments, rituals and dances in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang as an example to elaborate on China's Silk Road musical heritage and its effective protection. The Mogao Grottoes of Dunhuang are one of the four major grottoes in China and are part of the musical heritage of the Silk Road. From an archaeological point of view, the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang also have rich Buddhist art content and have great research value of ancient music culture. The total length of the Mogao Grottoes is about 1,600 meters from north to south, and its upper and lower arrangements reach a total of 5 layers. Overall, the arrangement of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang is staggered, orderly, and spectacular. It is currently China's largest, most complete and rich treasure house of ancient culture and art. At the same time, it is also a valuable site to help people understand the musical and cultural exchanges of the ancient Silk Road. In the Mogao Grottoes of Dunhuang, there are many murals related to the music culture of the Silk Road. For example, the mural contains many different musical instrument motifs. Through the musical instrument patterns, people can understand and interpret the musical culture exchange and integration between China and Europe on the Silk Road. In addition, people can also learn about the diversity of musical content in the context of the cultural exchange of music along the Silk Road (Lemus Delgado, 2023). Through the study of the varieties and types of musical instruments in the images of Dunhuang murals, archaeologists have found that the musical and cultural exchanges on the Silk Road have indeed provided many musical instrument resources for the continuous enrichment of the varieties and types of musical instruments in Chinese music. For example, in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang, there are not only many old musical instruments of people in the Central Plains, but also many musical instruments spread through countries along the Silk Road, and local musical instruments of Dunhuang (Franklin, 2023). In addition, there are many different types of musical instruments, and in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang, all kinds of musical instruments will have a variety of morphological characteristics. For example, The Early period of Tang Dynasty (AD 619~704), the various music and dance scenes depicted in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang contain 700 pipa and 55 different forms, and other musical instruments will also have a variety of morphological characteristics. The Middle period of Tang Dynasty (AD 755~781), the bands in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang often have many different

musical instrument combinations, which can also show the richness of the musical cultural heritage of China's Silk Road (Ganiev & Khamzin, 2023). Moreover, the shapes, forms, and performance methods of the different musical instruments in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang contain many connotations and values, and if further research can be carried out on them, it will be conducive to deepening people's impression of the musical, cultural heritage of the Silk Road. In addition, people can also effectively apply them to the modern cultural tourism industry or music industry to achieve better management and protection of musical cultural heritage.

Identify the Role and Form of Dunhuang Mural Musical Instruments

As part of China's Silk Road musical cultural heritage, the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang have a wide variety of musical instruments and different shapes. In addition, many musical instruments are recorded in ancient Chinese music historical materials. During the 1,000-year development of the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang, archaeologists found that it formed a total of more than 240 music-themed caves, and there are more than 4,500 musical instruments, a total of 40 musical instruments. After archaeology, people have analyzed the morphology and cultural characteristics of various musical instruments depicted in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang in detail. After analysis, it was found that the musical instruments in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang were basically from the countries of the Western Regions, the Central Plains, and Dunhuang itself. Studying the forms of musical instruments in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang will help people to recognize and understand the musical heritage of the Chinese Silk Road, and at the same time, deepen people's impression of the diversity of musical instruments at that time. In addition, to a certain extent, it can also reflect the musical richness and evolution of the Silk Road. Therefore, it will point out the direction for the management and protection of the musical cultural heritage of the Silk Road in future generations, as well as related research. And realize the understanding and collation of relevant information. In the Mogao Grottoes (AD 619~704) in the early Tang Dynasty, the form of solo playing. A single instrument performed the early murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang. It can be seen that in the early stage of the development of the Silk Road, the development of musical instruments in the musical culture of the Silk Road was not very mature. For example, in Cave No. 272 of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang, there is a mural, and there is a Tiangong musician in the painting playing a solo piece of pipa. For another example, in the murals of Cave No. 262 (Sui Dynasty), a Bodhisattva musician is depicted playing a solo performance of the five-stringed gourd qin, and his expression is indifferent and his artistic conception is leisurely (Jiang, 2023). In the Mogao Grottoes (AD 755~781) in the middle of the Tang Dynasty, the combination of performances. In the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang, there are also many murals in combination performance. Specifically, there are two types. First of all, it is played in combination with the same instruments, including the curved pipa, the big pipa, the small pipa, the five-stringed pipa, etc. Then there are the combinations of similar instruments, including pan flute, flute, sheng, pipa and ruan, zheng, etc. In the middle and late Tang Dynasty (AD 848~907), there are different combinations of instruments. For example, the combination of pipa-pan flute and the combination of transverse flute-clapper-pipa (Kallio, 2023) and the combination of sheng-pipa-drum-huqin. In the combination of different instruments, people can choose to play in two, three or four groups according to their own needs. At the same time, people can also choose to combine some Western Regions instruments and Central Plains instruments to play. In short, the combination of musical instruments is diverse and can be freely transformed. Therefore, this provides a lot of valuable information and content for future generations in terms of instrument combination, arrangement, and composition. It is worth studying for future generations.

Explore the Combination of Chinese and Western Musical Instruments along the Silk Road

In the Mogao Grottoes (AD 619~704) in the early Tang Dynasty, in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang, there is a lot of content depicting the lively performance scene of the band. From the lively scenes, archaeologists found that many of them belonged to the combination of warp and mutation. Moreover, the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang often depict many other different combinations, such as the Buddha backlight combination and the Fuxian change combination. By depicting different ensemble scenes, future generations can see the richness of the large and small combinations of different eras on the Silk Roads, and understand the diversity of their playing forms. In the Mogao Grottoes (AD 755~781) in the middle of the Tang Dynasty, in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang, there are more than 400 warp maps that have been depicted in various combinations, which also shows that the various combinations of cultures on the Silk Road are vibrant, and the scale is mainly characterized by the passage of time, gradually from small to large. For example, the Tiangong Rakuka Combination in Cave No. 272 (Beiliang) and the Yaocha Rakuka Combination in Cave No. 257 (Northern Wei Dynasty) are generally a combination of 3 to 12 people, and the scale is generally relatively small. From the late Northern Zhou Dynasty to the early Sui Dynasty, the scale of the assemblages shown in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes began to expand. For example, Cave 290 has 20 people, while Cave 200 has more than 25 people. It can be seen that with the gradual establishment of the Yan music system in the

court of the Sui Dynasty and under the effective formation of 7 and 9 music, the variety of musical instruments began to increase.

At the same time, the scale of the Sui Dynasty (AD 581~618) began to expand. In the prosperous and late Tang dynasties, the scale of the court group began to decrease again, and at the same time, the Yanle system was also declining, so the murals related to the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang on the Silk Road showed a lack of vitality. Generally speaking, the Mogao Grottoes mural assemblage during the Tang Dynasty comprised about 20-28 people, with a few people. Their musical instruments generally include sheng, pipa, zheng, recorder, square ring, gonghou, pan flute, waist drum, horizontal flute, etc. Moreover, the performance postures of various musicians on the murals are often extremely vivid and realistic, which can reflect the appearance of the court combination during the Tang Dynasty (AD 618~907).

Inherit the Cultural Connotations of the Musical Heritage of the Silk Roads

As mentioned above, China's Silk Road has left behind many brilliant musical and cultural heritages, which condense deep historical and cultural connotations. Therefore, it is necessary to adequately protect and manage the musical and cultural heritage of the Silk Roads. Only in this way can we better carry out the inheritance. In this process, the various pieces of information found by archaeologists play a crucial role. Moreover, it can also give people in later generations a lot of inspiration. Specifically, it is embodied in:

Understand the Relationship Between Religious Ceremonies and Various Musical Instruments

From an archaeological point of view, In the Mogao Grottoes (AD 755~781) in the middle of the Tang Dynasty, studying the musical heritage of the Silk Roads can provide a basis for studying the relationship between ancient religion and music. Many murals in the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang depict religious ceremonies and various musical instruments. Moreover, the frescoes' relationship between musical instruments and ancient rituals is exceptionally close and inseparable. Therefore, this can help later generations to have a deeper understanding of the evolution of musical rituals along the Silk Roads and the social context of different periods. Some scenes of musical instruments playing in religious ceremonies in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang also reveal the relationship between religious beliefs and musical culture. In this way, it will help future generations understand ancient music's key role in religious beliefs. And enrich the relevant records of music history.

Recreate the Ancient way of Playing and Combining

In the Mogao Grottoes (AD 619~704) in the early Tang Dynasty, archaeologists have also found many musical ritual scenes, musical instrument performance methods, and combination forms in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang. For example, some of the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang depict different court musician dances and musical instrument performance scenes, and the content can show the court music and dance of various dynasties during the development of the Silk Road. In this way, it provides much inspiration for traditional music performances and ensemble performances. In addition, people can also protect and pass on the performance techniques and combinations of ancient music. In the subsequent combination of cultural tourism, they will be applied to the economic development and cultural tourism innovation of the region to create different historical and cultural values for the local people. In the middle and late Tang Dynasty (AD 848~907). As part of the cultural musical heritage of the Silk Road, the various musical instruments and rituals, performance combinations, and combinations depicted in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang are of great value. Therefore, people should actively integrate relevant resources and use them to organize various activities related to the protection and inheritance of the music culture of the Silk Road. For example, music festivals or exhibitions of related musical instrument restorations, musicals, etc., can be held to use the Silk Roads' musical heritage better to boost tourism, cultural industries, regional economies, etc.

CONCLUSION

From the perspective of archaeology, the musical cultural heritage of China's Silk Road has excellent charm and characteristics and has always maintained great artistic vitality and inheritance value. Through the research in this paper, it should be recognized that from an archaeological point of view, the Mogao Grottoes in Dunhuang are a significant treasure trove of materials for the study of the music culture of the Silk Road therefore, in order to inherit better, protect and manage the musical and cultural heritage of the Silk Road. The results of the study show that the tunes of "Ni Clothes and Feather Clothes", "Qin Wang Breaking the Formation" and "Qin Yin Qing" have a single tune, but they have a sense of rhythm, and the changes in strength and weakness are similar to those in Europe. At the same time, the variation of the repertoire is high for "Qin Wang Breaking the Formation" and low for "Qin Yin Qing", which is similar to the traditional word card. At the same time, the golden bell contains

lead, tin and other elements, and the cooked skin technology of the Huqin is ahead of the Central Plains, similar to that of Europe, indicating that the Silk Road promoted exchanges between China and Europe, and deepened the connotation of Chinese music. In addition, the music of the Sui and Tang dynasties (AD 581~907) appeared in combinations, and the combination form was more reasonable, similar to that of European bands. At the same time, the musical heritage of musical instruments and repertoire in the Silk Road is confirmed in the murals of the Mogao Grottoes. This shows that the Silk Road promoted exchanges between China and the West, leaving behind a large amount of musical and cultural heritage.

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